

A genetic modification occurs when a person uses technology to alter an organism's genes. In today's paper I will dive into the world of genetic modifications and see whether they are ethical or not.

Today we will be classifying genetic modifications into three different types. Number one is genetically modifying humans. Number two is genetically modifying animals. And number three is genetically modifying plants.

Let's start with the effects of genetic modification. Genetic modification can be used to make fruits and vegetables larger or easier to grow. It can also be used in humans to potentially treat cancer or other genetic diseases. In animals such as pigs it can be used to fatten them up so that we can get more meat off of them.

While these all sound really cool they also come with a caveat. While a successful genetic modification can be great an unsuccessful attempt can be detrimental. For example these things could cause resistance from antibiotics, production of new toxins, new allergens in the food supply, and possibly unknown harms to our health. Afterall we still do not know all there is to know about genetic modifications.

In conclusion we should probably learn more about them on organisms such as plants and animals before genetically modifying human genes.

Citation

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